

Search strategy

1. search queries

PubMed :

((((((((((((((((((((((Diabetes Mellitus[MeSH Terms]) OR (diabetes mellitus, type 1[MeSH Terms])) OR (diabetes mellitus, type 2[MeSH Terms])) OR (diabetes[Title/Abstract])) AND (Lower Extremity[Title/Abstract])) OR (lower limb[Title/Abstract])) AND (amputation[MeSH Terms])) AND (Rehabilitation[MeSH Terms])) AND (Developing Countries[MeSH Terms])))) AND (multidisciplinarity[Title/Abstract])) OR (interdisciplinarity[Title/Abstract])) OR (transdisciplinarity[Title/Abstract])) OR (multidisciplinary[Title/Abstract])) OR (interdisciplinary[Title/Abstract])) OR (transdisciplinary[Title/Abstract])) OR (team-based care[Title/Abstract])) OR (healthcare team[Title/Abstract])) OR (team collaboration[Title/Abstract])) OR (interprofessional care team[Title/Abstract])) AND (model[Title/Abstract])) OR (approach[Title/Abstract]) AND ((booksdocs[Filter] OR guideline[Filter] OR observationalstudy[Filter] OR practiceguideline[Filter] OR review[Filter] OR systematicreview[Filter]) AND (humans[Filter]) AND (1990/1/1:2026/2/1[pdat]) AND (english[Filter])) AND ((booksdocs[Filter] OR guideline[Filter] OR observationalstudy[Filter] OR practiceguideline[Filter] OR review[Filter] OR systematicreview[Filter]) AND (humans[Filter]) AND (1990/1/1:2026/2/1[pdat]) AND (english[Filter])) **Filters:** Books and Documents, Guideline, Observational Study, Practice Guideline, Review, Systematic Review, English, Humans, Adult: 19+ years, Aged: 65+ years, Exclude preprints, from 1990/1/1 - 2026/2/1

Scopus :

("Diabetes Mellitus" OR "diabetes mellitus, type 1" OR "diabetes mellitus, type 2" OR "diabetes") AND ("Lower Extremity" OR "lower limb") AND (amputation) AND (Rehabilitation) AND ("Developing Countries") AND (multidisciplinary OR interdisciplinarity OR transdisciplinarity OR multidisciplinary OR interdisciplinarity OR transdisciplinary OR "team-based care" OR "healthcare team" OR "team collaboration" OR "interprofessional care team") AND (model OR approach) AND PUBYEAR > 1994 AND PUBYEAR < 2027 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English"))

Science Direct

("Diabetes Mellitus" OR "diabetes") AND ("lower limb") AND (amputation) AND (Rehabilitation) AND ("team-based care" OR "healthcare team" OR "team collaboration" OR "interprofessional care team")

Web of Science

TS = ("Diabetes Mellitus" OR diabetes AND "Lower Extremity" OR "lower limb" AND amputation AND Rehabilitation AND Developing Countries AND multidisciplinary* OR interdisciplinarity* OR transdisciplinary* OR "team-based care" OR "healthcare team" OR "team collaboration" OR "interprofessional care team" OR model OR approach)

Query link (web of science):

<https://www.webofscience.com/wos/woscc/summary/cf4c4b83-c7fa-4249-afe8-bcb6d18ae220-01a2f0ed15/relevance/1>

2. Results of the document search on each database

Database	number of documents found
PubMed	34177
Scopus	127
Science Direct	32
Web of Science	66912